

LIFE PREDICTION OF GLASS/VINYLESTER AND GLASS/POLYESTER COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

Steven L. Donaldson
WL/MLBM

Materials Directorate, Wright Laboratory
Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, OH 45433, USA

and

Ran Y. Kim

University of Dayton Research Institute
300 College Park Avenue
Dayton, OH 45469, USA

ABSTRACT

The use of composite materials in non-aerospace applications often require the prediction of composite strength and life over a much longer lifetime than has been traditionally studied for aerospace applications. The main objective of this paper is to validate the extension of a fatigue prediction methodology to estimate the life of composite laminates beyond the conventional S-N curve limit (10^6 cycles). To achieve this, a residual strength degradation model is used in conjunction with the S-N curve generated from low cycle fatigue tests of less than one million cycles. The two material systems investigated are glass fiber reinforced polyester and glass fiber reinforced vinylester composites, both having $[0/\pm 45]_{2S}$ ply orientations, which are used in blades for wind-power generators. The composites were tested in constant amplitude tension-tension fatigue. S-N curves were constructed from tests at four stress levels, with five specimens tested at each level. A statistical procedure was adopted for the evaluation of the fatigue strength wherein the fatigue data was assumed to follow both a classical power law and a two-parameter Weibull distribution. All fatigue data were pooled (the shape parameter was assumed to be constant and independent of the stress level) and the maximum-likelihood method used to estimate the Weibull parameters required for establishing statistical confidence and reliability. The S-N curves for the two material systems investigated are presented. The residual strength degradation model allows extrapolation of the experimentally derived S-N curves out to a large number of fatigue cycles without requiring time-consuming generation of additional fatigue data, and provides confidence for the prediction of fatigue life in service.

INTRODUCTION

As the structural applications of composites increase in non-traditional fields such as infrastructure, ground transportation, energy generation and medical implants, the life prediction of these materials under the corresponding service conditions deserve additional attention. Some structures, such as windmill blades used to generate energy from wind power, are expected to experience 10^8 to 10^9 fatigue cycles over their lifetime. This is well beyond the range where complete S-N curves can offer economical and timely predictions. With a 10 Hz testing frequency, it would take 116 to 1156 days per specimen to reach 10^8 to 10^9 cycles (which is prohibitively expensive as well as time consuming). A very useful tool, then, would be a validated method to

predict the extended fatigue life of a given class of composite materials based on economically feasible tests conducted at higher stress levels for shorter lifetimes.

FATIGUE TESTS

The two material systems investigated were glass fiber reinforced polyester and glass fiber reinforced vinylester composites. In both systems, the ply stacking sequence was $[0\pm 45]_{2S}$. The fiber volume content averaged 71% for both systems. Straight sided coupons, 2.5 cm, wide 15.2 cm long and 0.2 cm thick, were cut from a panel supplied by the manufacturer. Fatigue tests were conducted to obtain S-N curve relations under four constant stress levels corresponding to, for the glass/vinylester composites, 72.5, 60, 47.5, and 35 percent of the static strength of that system. Stress levels of 75, 62.3, 49.3, and 36.3 percent of the static strength were utilized in testing the glass/polyester composites. Five straight sided specimens under each stress level were fatigued until final failure at a frequency of 10 Hz with stress ratio of $R=0.1$. Static strength was determined by averaging ten specimens. In order to test the residual strength degradation model for this study, residual strength tests were also conducted for glass/polyester specimens at 25 percent of the static strength, which is smaller than the lowest stress level for the above S-N characterization. The specimen was fatigued to 100,000 cycles and then subjected to static loading until failure. The failure stress is defined as the residual strength. During this test, axial strain was monitored before fatigue and after fatigue with an extensometer.

LIFE PREDICTION MODEL

S-N Curve Relation

A classical power law representation of the S-N curve is given by

$$KS^bN=1 \tag{1}$$

where S is the maximum cyclic stress level, N is the number of loading cycles to failure, and b and K are empirically derived material constants. The logarithmic transformation of the Eqn (1) yields a straight line in the logS-logN plane. The constants K and b were determined from the fatigue life data using the method of least squares regression analysis.

Weibull Parameters Estimation

The two-parameter Weibull distribution has been widely used for modeling the static strength and fatigue life of composite materials. The Weibull cumulative distribution function, $F(x)$, is

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \tag{2}$$

where x is a random variable (static strength or fatigue life), α is shape parameter and β is scale parameter or characteristic life. The parameters α and β are estimated by the maximum likelihood method and are solutions of the maximum likelihood equation:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{\tilde{\alpha}} \ln x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{\tilde{\alpha}}} - \frac{1}{\tilde{\alpha}_i} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i}{n} = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$\tilde{\beta} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{\tilde{\alpha}} \right]^{1/\tilde{\alpha}} \tag{4}$$

The Newton-Raphson iterative method was employed for estimating α in Eqn 2. If desired, material allowables can be obtained using statistical procedures from the parameters estimated by the maximum likelihood method.

Strength degradation model

The residual strength degradation model for composite life prediction employed in this study is presented in refs [1,2]. The residual strength degradation model can predict the statistical distribution of fatigue life and the residual strength. For each stress level S , the residual strength, $X(n)$ after n fatigue cycles are related with the static strength, $X(0)$ by the following:

$$[X(n)]^c = [X(0)]^c - [\beta_0]^c K[S]^b n \quad (5)$$

In Eqn (5), fatigue frequency and stress ratio are assumed to be fixed. β_0 is the scale parameter of static strength (characteristic strength) and c is the ratio of the shape parameter of the static strength to that of fatigue life. Since the static strength distribution, $X(0)$ is assumed to have a Weibull distribution, the residual strength distribution, $X(n)$, and the fatigue life distribution, $R(n)$ can be expressed by combining Eqns (1), (2), and (5) are given by

$$X(n) = \exp \left[- \left(\left(\frac{X}{\beta_0} \right)^c + \frac{n}{1/KS^b} \right)^{\alpha_f} \right] \quad (6)$$

and

$$R(n) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{n}{1/KS^b} \right)^{\alpha_f} \right] \quad (7)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the Weibull parameter estimation for the static tension tests are given in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the distribution of static strength for both materials. The solid line is obtained from Eqn (2) using the estimated parameters from Table 1. The open symbols are test data plotted using, for the probability of survival, the method of median rank, where the probability of survival of the j th test specimen is $P_j = (j-0.3)/(m+0.4)$, for a sample size of m data points.

Table 2 summarize the fatigue test results. The shape parameter, α , appears to be independent of the stress level for both material system. The small variation of the shape parameter due to stress level is believed to be primarily due to the small sample size employed in this test. Thus, the shape parameter is assumed to be independent of stress level without performing a statistical test. The pooled shape parameter was estimated using the normalization method. The fatigue data for each stress level was normalized with the corresponding Weibull scale parameter and the normalized data was used to estimate the pooled shape parameter using Eqn (3). The scale parameters were recalculated with the pooled shape parameter using Eqn (4). The constants K and b in Eqn (1) were estimated from the pooled scale parameters using the least square regression analysis and are given in Table 3.

The S-N curves are shown in Figure 2 with the experimental data. The power law describes the fatigue life very well in the range of the stress investigated. The scatter of the data appears to be very small (relatively large value of α_f) compare to graphite epoxy composite systems ($\alpha_f \leq 2$).

In order to predict the fatigue life beyond the lowest stress level employed for obtaining the S-N characterization, the residual strength degradation model, Eqn (5) was used. In Eqn (5) the fatigue life for a given stress level S was calculated from the static strength data. The fatigue failure is assumed to be occur when the residual strength reduces to the maximum fatigue stress level. Thus in Eqn (5), by equating $X(n)$ and S , we calculate the fatigue life N for a given stress level. The calculated fatigue life data corresponding to the static strength are plotted in Figure 3 with the S-N curve (solid line) given in Figure 2. The open symbols represent the calculated life. The solid

symbols represent the experimental data for verification of the model. The dotted line is the linear extension of the S-N curve. The characteristic life obtained from the converted fatigue life data compares very well with the value obtained from the power law, as shown in Table 4.

Figure 4 shows the residual strength distribution for 10 glass polyester specimens after 100,000 cycles at 78.52 MPa. The solid symbols are experimental data plotted with median rank and the solid line is obtained from Eqn (6). The Weibull characteristic residual strength of the experiment and the prediction is 260 MPa and 298 MPa, respectively. The prediction appears to slightly over estimate the residual strength in this case. Further testing is required to draw any conclusion regarding this discrepancy.

CONCLUSIONS

Fiber-reinforced composite materials are now being used many less traditional, non-aerospace applications. In many of these applications, the prediction of the life of the materials under cyclic loading is critical. However, due to the high number of cycles required, the data required for lifetime predictions often exceed realistic limits of cost. To address this issue, an experimental study was undertaken to determine the validity of applying current life models to non-traditional systems and at high fatigue cycles. In this case, the fatigue performance of glass polyester and glass vinylester composites for wind generator blades were studied.

The classical power law was found to successfully describe the S-N relation for these composite systems. In addition, the residual strength degradation model, in conjunction with the S-N relation, was found to be very useful to obtain high cycle fatigue life predictions. This is significant in that economical and timely life predictions can be made with increased confidence.

REFERENCES

1. H.T. Hahn and R.Y. Kim, *J. Composite Materials*, Vol. 10, 1976, pp. 156-180.
2. J.N. Yang and M.D. Liu, *J. Composite materials*, Vol. 11, 1977, pp. 177-203.

Table 1 Static strength and Weibull parameters.

	<u>Mean, MPa</u>	<u>Weibull parameters</u>	
		<u>Shape, α</u>	<u>Scale, β</u>
Glass Vinylester	330	20.6	338
Glass Polyester	303	16.5	313

Table 2(a). Fatigue Test Data and Weibull Parameters for Glass/Vinylester.

Cyclic stress level (MPa)	Cycles to Failure	alpha	beta	Pooled beta (L=2.0864)
238.88	1244	2.482	1002	977
	276			
	865			
	694			
	1365			
197.69	4147	2.283	6032	6016
	2974			
	4723			
	10281			
	4884			
156.51	59221	2.168	37872	37594
	40636			
	12990			
	36078			
	18044			
115.32	1.03E+06	2.373	4.23E+05	5.92E+05
	2.68E+05			
	5.64E+05			
	3.04E+05			
	5.90E+05			
	4.19E+05			

Table 2(b). Fatigue Test Data and Weibull Parameters for Glass/Polyester.

Cyclic stress level (MPa)	Cycles to Failure	alpha	beta	Pooled beta (L=2.0864)
227.7	424	5.276	444	438
	378			
	551			
	303			
	394			
188.45	1326	4.789	1813	1808
	1525			
	1422			
	1747			
	2310			
149.19	3593	4.036	7667	7782
	8137			
	6802			
	6461			
	9683			
109.93	48916	4.102	66172	67172
	87691			
	63205			
	55737			
	45425			

Table 3. Material constants determined by regression analysis.

	K	b
Polyester/glass	1.571x10 ⁻¹⁹	6.8493
Vinylester/glass	1.865x10 ⁻²⁴	8.7116

Table 4. Predicted fatigue life.

	Fatigue stress	Predicted life, cycles	
	MPa	S-N curve	Eqn (5)
Polyester/glass	78.52	667,642	602,760
Vinylester/glass	82.37	10,957,666	9,647,100

Figure 1(a). Statistical Static Strength Distribution of Glass/Vinylester Specimens

Figure 1(b). Statistical Static Strength Distribution of Glass/Polyester Specimens

Figure 2. S-N Curve for Glass/Vinylester and Glass/Polyester.

Figure 3(a). High Cycle Prediction vs. Experimental Results in Glass/Vinylester.

Figure 3(b). High Cycle Prediction vs. Experimental Results in Glass/Polyester.

Figure 4. Residual Strength of Glass/Polyester after 10⁵ cycles at 78.52 MPa.